

Cys44 of SARS-CoV-2 3CL^{PRO} affects its catalytic activity

Ilaria Iacobucci^{a,b,1}, Irene Cipollone^{a,b,c,1}, Flora Cozzolino^{a,b}, Daniela Iaconis^c, Carmine Talarico^c, Gabriele Coppola^d, Stefano Morasso^e, Elisa Costanzi^e, Paolo Malune^f, Paola Storici^e, Enzo Tramontano^f, Francesca Esposito^{f,2}, Maria Monti^{a,b,*,2}

^a Department of Chemical Sciences, University of Naples "Federico II", Via Cintia, 21, 80126 Napoli, Italy

^b CEINGE Advanced Biotechnologies s.c.a r.l. "Franco Salvatore", Via Gaetano Salvatore 486, 80131 Napoli, Italy

^c Dompè Farmaceutici SpA, EXSCALATE, Via Tommaso De Amicis, 95, I-80131 Napoli, Italy

^d Institute Experimental Endocrinology and Oncology "Gaetano Salvatore" (IEOS), National Research Council (CNR), 80145 Naples, Italy

^e Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste, Structural Biology, Protein Targets for Drug Discovery Lab, SS 14 - km 163,5 in AREA Science Park, Basovizza, 34149 Trieste, Italy

^f Department of Life and Environmental Sciences, University of Cagliari, S.P. 8 Monserrato, Sestu Km 0.700, I-09042 Monserrato, Italy

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ABSTRACT

SARS-CoV-2 encodes a 3C-like protease (3CL^{PRO}) that is essential for viral replication. This cysteine protease cleaves viral polyproteins to release functional nonstructural proteins, making it a prime target for antiviral drug development. We investigated the inhibitory effects of halicin, a known c-Jun N-terminal kinase inhibitor, on 3CL^{PRO}. Mass spectrometry and crystallographic analysis revealed that halicin covalently binds to several cysteine residues in 3CL^{PRO}. As expected, Cys145, the catalytic residue, was found to be the most targeted residue by halicin. Secondly, Cys44 was found to be modified, suggesting a potential inhibitory role of this residue. A mutant protease (Cys44Ala) was generated to further understand the function of Cys44. *In silico* and enzymatic assays showed that the mutation significantly reduced the stability and activity of 3CL^{PRO}, indicating the importance of Cys44 in maintaining the active conformation of the protease. Differential scanning fluorimetry assays confirmed this evidence, showing a reduced thermal stability of the mutant compared to the wild-type protease. Our results highlight the potential of halicin as a multi-target inhibitor of 3CL^{PRO} and underline the importance of Cys44 in the function of the protease. These findings contribute to the development of effective antiviral therapies against COVID-19 by targeting critical residues in 3CL^{PRO}.

1. Introduction

Human coronaviruses represent a major group of CoVs associated with respiratory tract infections, ranging from common colds to severe pneumonia and bronchiolitis [1]. Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) emerged in December 2019, rapidly causing a global threat, leading the WHO to declare a pandemic on March 11, 2020. Despite its basic reproductive rate (R₀) being like SARS-CoV and pandemic influenza, the proportion of symptomatic individuals requiring hospital admission was five to six times higher [2].

The SARS-CoV-2 genome, similar to other β-coronaviruses, comprises 14 functional open reading frames (ORFs) that encode for nonstructural proteins (NSPs), accessory proteins, and structural proteins [3,4]. ORF1a and ORF1b encode polyproteins pp1a and pp1ab,

respectively, which are autoproteolytically processed by the papain-like protease (PL^{PRO}, nsp3) and the 3C-like cysteine protease (M^{PRO} or 3CL^{PRO}, nsp5) [5,6]. Notably, 3CL^{PRO}, a cysteine protease, hydrolyzes the polyprotein at a minimum of 11 sites, preferring Leu-Gln↓(Ser, Ala, Gly) (↓ marks the cleavage position) sequence, thereby releasing most of the functional NSPs [6].

Structurally, 3CL^{PRO} is a homodimer. In each monomer, we can recognize three domains: domain I (residues 8–100) and domain II (residues 101–183) are six-stranded antiparallel β barrels that enclose the substrate-binding site, while domain III (residues 198–303) is a cluster of five helices involved in the regulation of protein dimerization [7]. 3CL^{PRO} monomeric state is transient and less active than the dimeric form that acts as a stable functional unit [8]. The main residues involved in the catalytic mechanism are the Cys145 and the His41; additionally, a

* Corresponding author at: Department of Chemical Sciences, University of Naples "Federico II", Via Cintia, 21, 80126 Napoli, Italy.

E-mail address: montimar@unina.it (M. Monti).

¹ Equal contribution.

² Co-last author with Maria Monti.

water molecule forms a hydrogen bond with the histidine, acting as a third component in the active site [9]. Since this protease plays a pivotal role in the viral life cycle, it represents a primary target to fight SARS-CoV-2 diffusion. Consequently, considerable efforts have been made to identify specific 3CL^{pro} inhibiting agents.

Numerous drugs and molecules have been studied for their ability to inhibit 3CL^{pro}, including nirmatrelvir by Pfizer [10], with their effectiveness often dependent on covalent binding to residues in the active site, and mainly to the catalytic Cys145. However, the active site stability depends on the dimerization of 3CL^{pro} and the correct orientation of its subdomains. This breakthrough led Gunther et al. to identify two allosteric binding sites on the protein using X-ray crystallography to screen approximately 5000 compounds [11]. Most of the identified molecules (37) bind the active site of the enzyme covalently to Cys145, like tolperisone and GC376, or non-covalently, like MUT056399. Thirteen out of 37 molecules show binding activity at different sites.

The first allosteric binding site is a pocket composed mainly of hydrophobic residues (Ile213, Leu253, Gln256, Val297, and Cys300), located in the C-terminal domain responsible for dimerization, while the second allosteric binding site is the region between the catalytic and dimerization domains [11]. The first allosteric binding site is highly conserved, with 96 % sequence identity between SARS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 [12]. Key residues in this domain, like Arg4, Ser10, Gly11, Glu14, Asn28, Ser139, Phe140, Ser147, Glu290, Arg298, and Glu299, are responsible for destabilizing the SARS-CoV enzyme dimer when mutated, hampering functional activity (especially residues 290, 298, and 299) [12].

In the second domain, AT7519 interacts with Val202, Thr292, Ile249, and Phe294 through Van der Waals interactions and with Gln110 and Asp153 through hydrogen bonds. These interactions induce the reorientation of Asp153, with the movement of Tyr154 leading to the formation of a salt bridge with Arg298 [11], a crucial residue for the dimeric structure [13]. In fact, in the R298A mutant generated by Shi et al., a reorientation of the dimerization domain was determined, causing the destabilization of the S1 pocket [13]. In this context, Zhang and colleagues, performing *in silico* analysis based on molecular dynamics, demonstrated that two allosteric binders, Pelitinib and AT519, may induce a conformational change in the catalytic pocket, reducing substrate accessibility [14]. However, this finding has not yet been validated by experimental data, and more studies are needed to confirm this mechanism of action.

In this wide and intricate field, Exscalate4CoV (“EXaSCale smart pLatform Against paThogEns for CoronaVirus” or E4C; www.exscalate4cov.eu) steps in. Exscalate4CoV is an EU H2020-funded emergency project aimed at exploiting high-power computing and screening facilities to quickly identify clinical candidates against SARS-CoV-2 viral infections [9,15]. E4C is based on a supercomputing platform [16,17], where *in silico* high-throughput screenings are performed for the identification of potential targets and drugs. The main purpose of E4C is the repurposing of already available drugs in *preclinical* and clinical studies for SARS-CoV-2, leading to candidates' entrance in clinical trials with the help of cheminformatics and structural biologists [9].

Within this project, we recently reported the results of a screening campaign on 3CL^{pro} protein activity involving >8.7 K compounds. In addition to previously reported inhibitors of 3CL^{pro} protease, 62 other compounds with IC₅₀ values lower than 1 μM have been identified [9]. Among them, we found halicin (also known as SU3327) as a potential inhibitor of the SARS-CoV-2 main protease.

Interestingly, the 1,3,4-thiadiazole nucleus contained in the halicin structure (Fig. 1) is one of the most important and well-known heterocyclic nuclei, forming the basis of a variety of natural products and medicinal agents, and has been established as a pharmacologically significant scaffold [18].

Halicin has been found to inhibit the enzyme c-Jun N-terminal kinase (JNK), a member of the Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinase (MAPK) signaling pathway. This pathway is known to be involved in the

Fig. 1. Halicin chemical structure.

pathogenesis of many diseases [19], and dysregulation of JNK is linked to several pathological conditions, including type-2 diabetes, obesity, cancer, inflammation, and cardiac dysfunction [20–23]. Additionally, halicin has been recently proposed as an antibiotic against several pathogens, including *E. coli* [24], *S. aureus* [25], *A. baumannii* [26], *Enterococcus faecalis*, and *Enterococcus faecium* [27], and *Staphylococcus* [25,28]. In the context of COVID-19, it is known that its clinical severity is linked to cytokine storm and inflammasome activation [29–31], suggesting JNK inhibitors as potential therapeutic candidates [32].

The repurposing of halicin as a covalent inhibitor of 3CL^{pro} has been proposed by Yang and colleagues [33] through the description of the binding mechanism by native mass spectrometry and X-ray crystallography. The authors attributed the inhibition of 3CL^{pro} to the covalent binding of halicin with the catalytic cysteine (Cys145), but other cysteine residues reactive to the drug have also been described. Although blocking the catalytic residue causes loss of function of the SARS-CoV-2 protease, the other 11 cysteine residues might influence the protease's catalytic activity through different mechanisms.

In this study, we aimed to characterize the 3CL^{pro}-halicin complex by identifying and quantifying all the reactive cysteine residues through integrated *in silico*, macromolecular crystallography, and mass spectrometry approaches. Based on previous studies and our investigations, Cys145 was found the most targeted residue by halicin. Secondly, Cys44 was found modified, along with Cys85 and Cys300 at a lesser extent. To further understand the role of this residue, we expressed and purified a 3CL^{pro} mutant replacing the Cys44 with an Ala (Cys44Ala) and assessed its activity. Our findings indicate that this amino acid substitution reduces the stability of the active enzyme, suggesting a potential role for Cys44 in the reactivity of 3CL^{pro}.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. 3CL^{pro} expression, purification, and characterization

The wt 3CL^{pro} of SARS-CoV-2 plasmid was kindly provided by Prof. Rolf Hilgenfeld's research group at the Institute of Biochemistry, Center for Structural and Cell Biology in Medicine, University of Lübeck (Germany) (ORF1ab polyprotein residues 3264–3569, GenBank code: MN908947.3). Protein production and purification for crystallization followed the protocol reported by Zhang et al. 2020, with eluted fractions containing the target protein pooled and subjected to buffer exchange in 20 mM Tris-HCl, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, pH 7.8. The protein was flash frozen in LN2 at a concentration of 10–20 mg/ml and stored in aliquots at –80 °C.

The 3CL^{pro} wt protein for biochemical and differential scanning fluorimetry assays was expressed in the *E. coli* BL21(DE3) strain and purified using the protocol described in Costanzi et al. [34]. Briefly, the pellets were resuspended, clarified by ultracentrifugation and the supernatant was loaded for the first step in a Ni-Sepharose column and eluted with an Imidazole gradient. The fractions containing the protein were pooled and loaded in a HiTrap Q HP column for the second purification step and the protein was eluted with a salt gradient. The fractions containing the 3CL^{pro} wt protein were pooled and concentrated using Amicon Ultra 15 centrifugal filters, at 4000 g, at 4 °C, in a buffer exchange (20 mM Tris-HCl, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, and 1 mM DTT,

pH 7.8). Protein purity was verified by SDS-PAGE analysis and the protein solution was aliquoted and stored at -80°C .

The 3CL^{PRO} Cys44Ala mutant was expressed following the same procedure previously described for the wt. However, the purification was carried out using a single step on a Ni-Sepharose column, as this approach provided sufficient protein purity for analysis. Additionally, further purification steps were avoided, as they were found to negatively affect the protein's stability and activity.

Both recombinant proteins were characterized by mass mapping strategies involving *in situ* hydrolysis of the band fractionated by SDS-PAGE and LC-MS/MS analysis, according to Cozzolino et al. [35].

2.2. Identification and relative quantification of 3CL^{PRO} modifications induced by halicin

The reaction of 3CL^{PRO} with halicin was performed by incubating the native protein with halicin in a 1:1 (10 μM) molar ratio with the monomeric form of the protein for 30 min at room temperature (buffer: 20 mM Tris, pH 7.8, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA). An aliquot of the sample was analyzed by LC-MS a Q-ToF Premier (Waters, Milford, MA, USA) mass spectrometer coupled with an 1100 Agilent HPLC (Palo Alto, California, US) [36] to verify the reaction and determine the number of molecules that had reacted with each 3CL^{PRO}.

The mass mapping procedure for identifying modified residues involved setting up a pepsin hydrolysis protocol. The optimal hydrolysis conditions consisted of a 1:50 w/w enzyme/substrate ratio for 2 h [37]. The peptide mixtures were then analyzed by nano LC-MS/MS using a LTQ Orbitrap XL mass spectrometer according to previously reported protocols [35]. Peptide identification was carried out with the Mascot software as previously described [38]. The halicin molecular weight addition was inserted in the in-house software, and modified peptides were searched for variable modifications on cysteine residues. The relative quantification of halicin-modified peptides was performed using the extracted ion chromatogram (XIC) procedure. Specifically, the current of each peptide ion (modified and unmodified) was extracted from the whole chromatogram, and the area of the corresponding chromatographic peak was measured and employed as quantitative parameter. The percentage of modified species was calculated as reported in formula (1).

Percentage of cysteine modification

$$\% \text{Cys}_x \text{ modification} = \frac{\sum (\text{Area of all peptide ions with Cys}_x \text{ modified by halicin})}{\sum (\text{Area of all peptide ions containing modified and not modified Cys}_x)} * 100 \quad (1)$$

Cys_x corresponds to the specific cysteine under investigation.

2.3. Crystallization, data collection, data reduction, structure determination, refinement and final model analysis

Prior to crystallization 3CL^{PRO} wt was incubated at a concentration of 5 mg/ml (148 μM) with halicin at molar ratio of 1:2 for 1 h (5 % DMSO final). Crystals were obtained at RT after 1–2 days with the vapour diffusion technique, in sitting drops, using seeding and 0.09 M NPS (Sodium nitrate, Sodium phosphate dibasic, Ammonium sulfate), 0.1 M HEPES/Mops pH 7.5, 20 % v/v PEG 500 MME, 10 % w/v PEG 20000 as a precipitant solution. Diffraction data were collected at 100 K, at the XDR2 beamline of the Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste using a 1.000 Å wavelength.

The collected dataset was processed with XDS [39] and Aimless [40] from the CCP4 suite [41]. The structure was solved by molecular replacement with Phaser [42] using as a search model 7BB2 (PDB ID).

The initial model was refined alternating cycles of manual model building in COOT [43] and automatic refinement using Phenix [44]. Data collection and refinement statistics are reported in Supplementary Table S1.

2.4. In vitro enzymatic activity assays

The activity of 3CL^{PRO} wt and Cys44Ala was measured using a FRET method [34]. The assay was performed in a 384-well black plate with a reaction volume of 20 μl containing 20 mM Tris (pH 7.3), 100 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT, 1 mM EDTA, and various concentrations of tested compounds. After a 30-min incubation at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 12 μM of DABCYL-KTSAVLQ↓SGFRKM-EDANS substrate was added to each well, and the fluorescent signal was read after 15 min of incubation at room temperature at Ex 340 nm and Em 490 nm. Kinetic experiments were performed using the same conditions described in this paragraph for the biochemical assay, but the signal was read for 30 min and the Kinetic parameters calculated using the Michaelis-Menten plot of GraphPad Prism software.

2.5. Differential scanning fluorimetry assay

The stability of 3CL^{PRO} wt and Cys44Ala mutant proteins was evaluated using a differential scanning fluorimetry (DSF) assay [46]. The assay was performed in a 50 μl reaction containing 20 mM HEPES pH 7.8, 120 mM NaCl, and 2 μM of 3CL^{PRO} wt or Cys44Ala mutant proteins. The reactions were pre-incubated with 40 μM of compounds for 30 min at room temperature. After adding 5 \times SYPRO Orange dye, thermal denaturation from 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 95 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ was initiated at a scan rate of 1.5 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, and the thermal shift (ΔTm) was calculated as described [47].

2.6. Native gel electrophoresis

The conformational analysis of 3CL^{PRO} wt and mutant conformers was carried out by native gel electrophoresis as previously described [48]. Briefly, 5 μg of protein were loaded in a buffer containing Tris-HCl (pH 7.8), 150 mM NaCl, and 1 mM EDTA onto a 10 % 0.5SAR-PAGE running gel at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Following electrophoresis, the gel was stained with colloidal Coomassie Blue for 1 h, and the excess dye was removed by washing in deionized water for 12 h.

2.7. Molecular dynamics simulation

To evaluate the structural stability of the protein and explore its conformational space, molecular dynamics (MD) simulations were performed for 500 ns. The MD simulations were conducted using the Desmond Multisim protocol [49]. The entire system was solvated in an orthorhombic box, with a 10 Å buffer of TIP3P (transferable intermolecular potential three-point) water molecules, and Na⁺ counterions were added to neutralize the system's net charge. This resulted in a total of 37,186 atoms. During the initial phase, the Multisim method facilitated the equilibration and relaxation of the structure, simulating a mature system. The simulation was performed under constant pressure of 1 atm and a temperature of 310 K, with thermostating and barostating applied using the Martyna–Tobias–Klein method. The coupling constants for the thermostat and barostat were set to 0.5 ps and 2.0 ps, respectively. Hydrogen positions were constrained using the M-SHAKE algorithm, enabling a time step of 2 fs. Long-range electrostatic

interactions were calculated at each time step using the Particle Mesh Ewald (PME) method, with a cut-off radius of 10 Å.

3. Results

3.1. Mass spectrometry characterization of 3CL^{pro}-halicin adducts obtained in sub-stoichiometric conditions

To determine whether residues other than the catalytic cysteine are involved in halicin binding, thereby impairing the catalytic activity of 3CL^{pro}, the recombinant protein was treated with a micromolar concentration of halicin (10 µM). Specifically, a 1:1 M ratio of 3CL^{pro} monomer (3CL^{proM}) to halicin was used, and the incubation was carried out for 30 min. Subsequently, we analyzed the modified protein mixture by LC-ESI-MS to confirm halicin binding and to characterize the resulting species.

As shown in Fig. 2, the ESI-MS spectrum revealed the occurrence of a single species with a molecular weight of $33,926.66 \pm 0.93$ Da, consistent with monomeric 3CL^{pro} modified by one halicin molecule. This finding aligns with the results reported by Yang et al. We observed an increase of +128 Da on the expected average molecular weight of 3CL^{pro} (33,796.6 Da), attributable to the covalent modification of a cysteine residue with one halicin molecule, through an aromatic nucleophilic substitution mechanism [33].

An aliquot of the reaction mixture underwent a mass mapping procedure to localise the halicin-induced modification on the 3CL^{pro} sequence. Initially, we applied a classical digestion protocol including the carboamidomethylation of free cysteines followed by trypsin digestion in 50 mM ammonium bicarbonate, pH 8. Unexpectedly, no peptide containing modified cysteines was detected in these conditions, suggesting the intrinsic instability of the adduct in mild basic conditions. In order to avoid the dissociation of the covalent adduct with halicin and prevent scrambled disulfide bridge formation, it was necessary to employ a proteolytic protocol effective in acidic conditions. An aliquot of the modified protein was therefore digested with pepsin, a digestive proteolytic enzyme active at acidic pH (around pH 2); the resulting peptide mixture was analyzed by nanoLC-MS/MS. Pepsin's broad specificity makes it particularly useful for efficiently identifying this kind of

modifications. However, the MS/MS spectra of peptides resulting from pepsin digestion are often poor in quality and challenging to interpret.

As expected, we found Cys145 modified within various peptides generated by pepsin digestion (see Supplementary Table S2). Surprisingly, Cys44, Cys85, and Cys300 were also found covalently bound to halicin. Based on this finding, we hypothesized that under the explored experimental conditions (10 µM halicin), a heterogeneous population of mono-modified 3CL^{pro}-halicin adducts is generated, as suggested by the ESI-MS spectrum. To assess the contribution of each cysteine residue to the modified 3CL^{pro} fraction, we quantified the extent of modification for each cysteine-containing peptide (Supplementary Table S2). Quantification was performed using the ion extracted chromatogram (XIC) procedure [35]. Specifically, we summed the chromatographic peak areas of all peptide species containing a given modified cysteine and divided this by the sum of the areas of all modified and unmodified peptides containing that residue. The amount of each modified cysteine was expressed as percentages and shown in Table 1.

As expected, Cys145 was the most targeted by the drug, reaching approximately 47 % of modification. The second cysteine residue with the highest percentage of modification was Cys44 (12.31 %), while Cys85 and Cys300 appeared less modified (7.02 % and 4.85 %, respectively). These results highlight an unexpected reactivity of these other Cys residues in addition to the catalytic one, suggesting that a combination of mechanisms may be responsible for 3CL^{pro} inhibition, beyond the blockage of Cys145.

3.2. Crystal structure of 3CL^{pro}/halicin

We obtained co-crystals of 3CL^{pro} together with halicin and the x-ray structure was solved in space group P212121 at 1.93 Å resolution, containing one dimer in the a.u. (see Supplementary Table S1 for data collection and refinement statistics). The overall structure (PDB ID: 7NBY) is preserved and the C-alpha trace well overlaps with the 7TUU structure obtained using crystal soaking techniques by Yang et al. (RMSD 0.529 Å) [33]. As for 7TUU, we also identified in 2fo-c map multiple covalent derivatizations of solvent accessible cysteines by halicin while despite several trials, we never obtained crystals of halicin bound only to the catalytic Cys145, as could have been expected (Figs. 3, S3). In each site, the ligand has reacted releasing the thiadiazol-amine and leaving the nitrothiazole-group covalently bound to the Sulphur, according to our MS results and published data (Fig. 3).

Interestingly, besides the derivatization on the highly exposed Cys156 and Cys300, in the active site we could identify that halicin derivatized not only the catalytic Cys145 but also the Cys44 (Fig. 3). This binding was not observed in 7TUU structure, where the electron density map in the active site clearly shows Cys145 bound to the nitrothiazole of halicin, while Cys44 has a less defined density map being at the edge of an unfolded α-helix in the P2 pocket, as underlined by Yang et al. In our 7NBY structure, both active sites of the dimer are involved, however they show a different situation: in chain A all the residues of the active site are visible in the electronic densities and both Cys44 and Cys145 have reacted with halicin, having a well-defined electron density, as shown in left insert in Fig. 3. In chain B, however, residues 46–52 are not visible in the electronic density, and histidine 41 rotates, making a stacking interaction with the ring of halicin bound to the catalytic Cys145(B) (Fig. 3, right insert). The nitrothiazole group bound to both

Fig. 2. Transformed ESI spectrum of the reaction product of 3CL^{proM} with halicin in a 1:1 molar ratio.

Table 1
Quantification results of halicin-modified cysteine residues by the XIC method.

Cysteine residue	%Cys modification
Cys44	12.31
Cys85	7.02
Cys145	46.45
Cys300	4.85

Fig. 3. Cartoon model of the crystal structure of the dimer of 3CL^{PRO} (PDB ID 7NBY, chain A = light blue, chain B = light green) with halicin bound to cysteines 44, 145, 156 and 300 of both chains shown as sticks and colored in magenta. Left inset: active site of chain A with derivatized Cys145 and Cys44 in magenta contoured by 2Fo-fc map and catalytic His41 colored in teal. Right insert: active site of chain B with derivatized Cys145 and Cys44 in magenta contoured by 2fo-fc map and catalytic His41 is shown in sticks and colored in orange. 2Fo-Fc maps are shown in dashed blue lines contoured at 1 sigma. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

cysteines can also be modelled in the B-chain, although the map of the Cys44-bound ring is less well defined and points outwards. It is worth noting that the B-chain active site of our structure better resembles the halicin-bound Cys145 and the His41 observed in 7TUU (Fig. S4). In contrast, in the A-chain active site, His41 adopts the same orientation as in the Apo structure (PDB ID: 7BB2) (Fig. S5).

These data confirm the well reported flexibility and adaptability of 3CL^{PRO} active site and the observed asymmetrical behavior of the two active sites in the dimer [50]. Moreover, the lack of electron density for the region 46–52 may further suggest a destabilizing effect due to halicin derivatization.

3.3. Assessment of the role of Cys44 on 3CL^{PRO} enzymatic activity

While the importance of Cys145 is well known since this residue is essential for enzyme activity, the role of Cys44 has been less investigated and hence we wanted to evaluate it by generating a mutant of the protein containing an alanine residue in position 44, instead of cysteine. Halicin compound was tested for its inhibitory activity against 3CL^{PRO} wt in comparison with Cys44 Ala mutant; the compound GC376 was employed as positive control. As shown in Table 2, halicin affects the 3CL^{PRO} wt enzymatic activity with an IC₅₀ value of 0.45 μM.

Moreover, the inhibition occurs in a dose-dependent manner (Fig. 4A), with a profile that decreases in the presence of increasing

Table 2
Effect of halicin compound on 3CL^{PRO} wt and Cys44Ala mutant.

Compound	SARS-CoV-2 3CL ^{PRO} IC ₅₀ ^a (μM)	
	wt	Cys44Ala
Halicin	0.45 ± 0.04	6.52 ± 1.02
GC376	0.24 ± 0.03	0.24 ± 0.07

^a Compound concentration required to reduce enzyme activity by 50 %.

concentration of compound, like the control GC376 (Fig. 4B). Therefore, we evaluated if the mutation Cys44Ala had effects on the enzymatic activity, by carrying out the same biochemical assays. Results reported in Table 2 show that halicin inhibits 3CL^{PRO} Cys44Ala mutant with an IC₅₀ value of 6.52 μM. These data demonstrate that when Cys44 is not available to bind halicin, as in the case of the Cys44Ala mutant, the inhibition occurs with an effectiveness that decreases up to 14 folds in comparison with 3CL^{PRO} wt (Table 2). The effect of the Cys44Ala mutation in SARS-CoV-2 3CL^{PRO} has been further supported by the different kinetic constants obtained in comparison to the wt protein. Specifically, the 3CL^{PRO} wt showed a K_M of 14 μM, whereas the Cys44Ala mutant displayed a K_M of 78 μM. When Michaelis-Menten analysis at different substrate concentrations for the two proteins was performed, we obtained a k_{cat} of 7.17 min⁻¹ and 0.2 min⁻¹ for the 3CL^{PRO} wt and the Cys44Ala mutant, respectively. The k_{cat}/K_M ratio was calculated as 0.51 min⁻¹ μM⁻¹ for the 3CL^{PRO} wt and 0.002651 min⁻¹ μM⁻¹ for the 3CL^{PRO} Cys44Ala. These data highlight that the affinity of the mutant for the substrate is >5 times lower than the wt, and its catalytic efficiency is about 200 times lower than the wt.

3.4. Assessment of the effect of Cys44 on 3CL^{PRO} conformation via MD simulation approach

The Molecular Dynamics (MD) approach was applied to understand the effects of the Cys44Ala mutation on the 3CL^{PRO} monomer structure, taking into account the dynamic of the protein. The values of Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSD) and Root Mean Square Fluctuation (RMSF) were evaluated to identify the differences between the wild type of form and the Cys44Ala mutant of 3CL^{PRO} monomers, during the simulation.

RMSD values (Fig. 5A) showed how the wt monomer maintains a good degree of global stability (RMSD range 1.5 to 3.5 Å), while the mutated shape undergoes important conformational alterations (RMSD range 1.0 to 5.5 Å), especially in the final part of the simulation (TIME >

Fig. 4. (A) Dose-dependent curve of halicin in the presence of 3CL^{PRO} wt and 3CL^{PRO} Cys44Ala mutant. (B) Dose-dependent curve of GC376 in the presence of 3CL^{PRO} wt and 3CL^{PRO} Cys44Ala mutant.

Fig. 5. (A) Plot showing the RMSD trend in both wt (green) and Cys44Ala mutant monomer (blue) of 3CL^{PRO}. (B) RMSF trend in both wt (green) and Cys44Ala mutant monomer (blue) of 3CL^{PRO}. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

300 ns).

Alterations in the range of 1–3 Å found for the 3CL^{PRO} wt are expected for small, globular proteins. However, more significant changes, like

those observed in the case of mutant, suggest that the protein is experiencing a substantial conformational shift during the simulation.

Root Mean Square Fluctuation (RMSF) data emphasise that residues

Fig. 6. Differential scanning fluorimetry. (A) 3CL^{PRO} wt (in red). (B) 3CL^{PRO} wt (in red) in the presence of GC376 (in blue). (C) 3CL^{PRO} wt (in red) in the presence of halicin (in green). (D) 3CL^{PRO} Cys44Ala mutant (in red). (E) 3CL^{PRO} Cys44Ala mutant (in red) in the presence of GC376 (in blue). (F) 3CL^{PRO} Cys44Ala mutant (in red) in the presence of halicin (in green). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

that fall into the region around Cys44 (Fig. 5B), have a high degree of mobility. This could explain the ease of functionalisation that the Cys44 faces. In the presence of the mutation in Ala44, the same region is still exposed and appears stable. An overall reduction in monomer flexibility is also appreciated in the simulation of the wt protein when the Cys44 is covalently bound to the halicin (Fig. S1). Taken together these simulations suggested that the Cys44 can be easily reached by the ligand and the mutation in this residue significantly affect the functional globular conformation of the monomer.

3.5. Assessment of the effect of Cys44 on 3CL^{pro} stability via DSF analysis

To evaluate whether the Cys44Ala substitution can affect the stability of the protein, a Differential Scanning Fluorimetry (DSF) assay was carried out. By comparing the profiles of wt and mutant proteins (Fig. 6A and D), the mutant showed a significant lowering in melting temperature, estimated as -9°C in comparison to the wt (Table 3). This data suggests that also in absence of any drugs, the Cys44Ala mutant is less stable than the 3CL^{pro} wt.

In the presence of halicin, the thermal profiles of both 3CL^{pro} wt and Cys44Ala mutant changed with a different impact on the two proteins. On 3CL^{pro} wt, halicin provides a thermal negative shift of -6°C (Fig. 6C) in comparison to the not treated protein (Table 3). This behavior, completely different from that recorded in the presence of GC376 (Fig. 6B), another covalent inhibitor of the 3CL^{pro} wt used as a positive control, which has no effects on the wt protein stability (Table 3). Differently, when 3CL^{pro} Cys44Ala mutant is treated with halicin, the DSF profile showed a positive shift comparable to that recorded in the presence of GC376. These latter findings suggest that in the absence of Cys44, the apparent effect induced by halicin treatment aligns with that of GC376.

3.6. Evaluation of the effects of the Cys44Ala mutation on the 3CL^{pro} monomer-dimer equilibrium

Recognizing the importance of Cys44 in 3CL^{pro} stability, we explored its potential effect on the monomer-dimer equilibrium, as already described by Silvestrini et al. [51], by using native polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis [48]. This method, employing sodium lauroyl sarcosinate (sarkosyl, SAR) at 0.05 % w/v concentration, effectively resolves oligomeric states in the gel. As shown in Fig. 7, the recombinant proteins 3CL^{pro} wt and the Cys44Ala mutant exhibited different distributions between monomeric and dimeric states. The wt protein displayed two bands with apparent molecular weights around 65 kDa and 37 kDa, corresponding to those expected for the dimeric and monomeric forms, respectively. In contrast, the Cys44Ala mutant lacked the dimer band, indicating that this mutation directly affects the stability of the active dimeric form of 3CL^{pro}. This finding is consistent with differential scanning fluorimetry assay and biochemical assay results and lead us to make hypothesis on a possible role of Cys44 on 3CL^{pro} monomer-dimer equilibrium.

4. Discussion

3CL^{pro}, also known as the main protease (M^{pro}), is a cysteine protease that cleaves the viral polyprotein at 11 conserved sites, generating the

Table 3

Biophysical activities of 3CL^{pro} WT and Cys44Ala mutant in the presence of Halicin and GC376 compounds.

Compound	DSF T _m (°C)		ΔT _m (Cys44Ala-WT)
	WT	Cys44Ala	
Protein alone	51	42	-9
Halicin	45	48	+3
GC376	56	47	-9

Fig. 7. Sodium lauroyl sarcosinate (sarkosyl, SAR) 0.05 % gel of 3CL^{pro} wt and Cys44Ala proteins. The image shows the conformers' resolution of wt and mutant enzyme (5 μg each). Protein molecular weight markers are shown on the left side of the gel image.

functional units of the non-structural viral proteins required for viral replication. Given its central role in the viral life cycle, 3CL^{pro} inhibition by pharmacological drugs is an attractive target for antiviral therapy [52,53]. Besides the catalytic cysteine (Cys145), the other 11 cysteine residues in the 3CL^{pro} structure also play significant roles, contributing to the structural stability and proper folding of the enzyme, ensuring its functional integrity [8,53]. In this context, drug repurposing and the identification of mechanisms beyond catalytic inactivation could pave the way for novel antiviral agents. Within the Exscalate4CoV project, we *in silico* predicted 62 potential inhibitors of 3CL^{pro}, identifying halicin among them. Yang and colleagues [33] proposed halicin repurposing for the inhibition of 3CL^{pro}, describing the halicin binding mechanism through native mass spectrometry and X-ray crystallography. They found that Cys145, Cys156, and Cys300 were affected by halicin binding. However, they primarily focused on Cys145 inactivation as the key factor in 3CL^{pro} inhibition by the drug.

In this study, we confirmed halicin covalent binding through a nucleophilic aromatic substitution (S_NAr) mechanism and investigated whether other cysteine residues might also contribute to 3CL^{pro} inhibition by using biochemical and biophysical integrated approaches. Surprisingly, by mass spectrometry analysis, we found four cysteine residues modified upon halicin addition (Cys44, Cys85, Cys145, and Cys300) and, among them, Cys44 is the most abundant after Cys145. This result well aligns with the X-ray co-crystal structure presented here (PDB ID: 7NYB, <https://doi.org/10.2210/pdb7NYB/pdb>). Cys44 is reported highly nucleophilic due to its deprotonation at physiological pH [54]. This site is attractive due to its proximity to the catalytic pocket, and Verma et al. hypothesized the development of new small molecules with two weakly electrophilic warheads targeting both Cys44 and Cys145 for superior potency [54].

Additionally, we supported the functional role of Cys44 observing a

14-fold loss of potency of the mutated form (Cys44Ala mutant) *versus* the wt protein in a well-established enzymatic assay, corroborating the theory that Cys44 plays a key role in halicin's inhibitory mechanism beyond simple competition for catalytic cysteine binding with the substrate.

We thus evaluated the effects of the Cys44Ala mutation and halicin binding on 3CL^{PRO} conformation through both Molecular Dynamic (MD) simulation and Differential Scanning Fluorimetry (DSF) approach. The computational analysis revealed a higher relevant fluctuation level of the Cys44Ala mutant in comparison with wt protein, suggesting that the mutation might have an impact overall the protein structure. The simulation largely agrees with the DSF results that show significant differences between wt and mutant enzymes melting temperatures suggesting that the Cys44Ala mutant is inherently less stable than the wt protein. These results strengthen the role that Molecular Dynamics (MD) and related methods are close to becoming routine computational tools for drug discovery. They can be used to predict druggable binding sites as well as the behavior of the proteins, domains and residues in different conditions, thus accelerating and driving the process of drug-design [55–59].

This finding is intriguing as 3CL^{PRO} cysteine residues are generally more conserved, with Cys156 and Cys160 being the most variable among the 12 [60], highlighting the importance of the thiol group.

This observation is in line with the fact that the 3CL^{PRO} cysteine residues exhibit different physical and chemical properties, making them susceptible to modification by potential drugs. The three most exposed cysteines are Cys85, Cys145, and Cys156 [61], while it has been demonstrated that Cys22 and Cys44 are more nucleophilic than Cys145 [54]. Moreover, also myricetin, another effective drug, can covalently bind Cys44, which is part of the Cys44-Pro52 loop located near the active site of the protein and responsible for its stability [63]. Additionally, Xiong and colleagues [64] proved that the covalent inhibition of Cys300, situated at the dimeric interface, may disrupt the active conformation of 3CL^{PRO}, shifting the equilibrium towards the inactive monomer. This evidence suggests that not only Cys145 but also several other cysteine residues hold promise as potential antiviral targets for treating COVID-19.

Recent work by Ravanfar et al. [60] demonstrated that mutating the three most solvent-exposed cysteines (Cys85, Cys156, and Cys300) did not affect 3CL^{PRO}'s homodimeric structure or enzyme activity. However, our findings showed both the loss of the 3CL^{PRO} homodimeric structure and loss of activity in the Cys44Ala mutant, underlining the importance and the specificity of Cys44 role in enzyme functionality.

Finally, unlike the wt enzyme, the Cys44Ala mutant displayed an upshift in melting temperature with both halicin and GC376, the control compounds that exclusively binds Cys145 [65,66]. This observation suggests that without Cys44, halicin does not affect protein conformation, but maintains its primary effect, blocking Cys145 but not destabilizing the quaternary structure, as well as GC376.

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that, despite halicin predominantly targets Cys145, alternative cysteine residues can contribute to 3CL^{PRO} inhibition through different mechanisms. Our findings suggest an important role for Cys44 in supporting the catalytic activity of 3CL^{PRO}, through a stabilizing effect of monomer and therefore, on the consequent active dimer formation. The substitution of Cys44 with an alanine residue induces a local alteration which also has a long-range impact on protein conformation and on monomer-dimer equilibrium. Alterations in the 3CL^{PRO} monomer-dimer equilibrium by small molecules have been explored for developing SARS-CoV-2 antiviral agents. Silvestrini et al. [51] identified two molecules capable of shifting the equilibrium constant towards the monomer (called **6** and **7** by the authors) and they also characterized their interaction sites on the protein. Notably, only molecule **7** showed promising inhibition effects. The compound **6** displayed six contact sites located in the amino acidic region spanning from Leu141 to Gln192, while **7** had additional six contacts in the region from Thr24 to Met49. The latter strongly suggests that the enhanced

inhibitory activity maybe be mediated by the interaction with this region of 3CL^{PRO}, supporting our data indicating Cys44 as a functional residue for 3CL^{PRO} catalytic inactivation. In conclusion, our work confirmed the covalent binding of halicin to 3CL^{PRO} at Cys145, justifying its competitive inhibition mechanism, and demonstrated for the first time that Cys44, also targeted by halicin, is a key residue in the 3CL^{PRO} homodimeric protein stability and activity.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ilaria Iacobucci: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Irene Cipollone:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation. **Flora Cozzolino:** Methodology, Investigation. **Daniela Iaconis:** Writing – original draft, Resources. **Carmin Talarico:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Gabriele Coppola:** Writing – original draft. **Stefano Morasso:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Elisa Costanzi:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Paolo Malune:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Paola Storici:** Writing – original draft, Resources. **Enzo Tramontano:** Resources, Formal analysis. **Francesca Esposito:** Writing – original draft, Resources, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Maria Monti:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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